

PRODUCTIVITY ENHANCEMENT BY ADVANCED LEAN PRODUCTION SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Lean manufacturing is a systematic approach to manufacturing operations which saves time, money, and resources by concentrating on decreasing the waste during the part manufacturing. It can improve overall business performance as well as quality of produced parts by decreasing the wastes in processes and resources to increase added values in process of part production. As a result, lean manufacturing can produce advanced manufacturing systems with fewer faults and errors, less waiting, and less complexity in the process of part production. The lean manufacturing systems can be applied to the virtual manufacturing, sustainable manufacturing, supply chain and industry 4.0 in order to enhance the efficiency levels of part production. To manage the resources in the process of part production, knowledge management systems can be applied to the lean production. Advanced assembly lines in the automotive and ship industries can be generated in order to decrease the waste time and energy in assembly process of part production. A review of the implementations of lean production techniques in enhancing part manufacturing efficiency is provided and future research works are also suggested. The study's main goal is to provide a beneficial study for researchers in the field by providing an overview of current research on productivity enhancement using advanced lean production systems. It has been discovered that by reading and analyzing current successes in published papers, the research field can be advanced.

Keywords: Lean manufacturing, Productivity enhancement, Industry 4.0, Advanced supply chain

1. INTRODUCTION

Lean manufacturing is a concept of waste reduction by increasing productivity in industrial operations. Cost of produced parts, timeline and production resources all suffer as a result of waste during process of part manufacturing. The imposed waste during the manufacturing process adds little value to items or services which should be minimized in terms of productivity enhancement of manufacturing engineering. Lean manufacturing eliminates any waste that might detract from the company's value in order to increase productivity in part production processes, Hardcopf et al. (2021). Lean manufacturing is an efficiency-based methodology that focuses on streamlining processes to reduce waste and use advanced technologies in order to improve productivity of manufacturing systems by modifying or changing pre-existing ideas, Lukman and Salim (2017).

The initial objective of the lean production is removing all of a company's unneeded and pricey elements which cannot provide added values in the final products. The goal of lean manufacturing is to have a continuous flow of all production operations with as little waste as possible, Grewal (2008). The main aim of lean manufacturing is to increase productivity in process of part production by decreasing the waste in resources and used materials. It is developed in order to provide materials and methodologies which are required in the appointed time and locations based on the accurate scheduling of manufacturing orders, Jon et al. (2000); Goshime et al. (2018).

Reduced lead times, lower operating costs, and improved product quality are just a few of the advantages of lean manufacturing. Other advantages include fewer defects and rework (both in-house and at the customer), lower inventory, higher stock turnover, less space, higher efficiencies, more output per man hour, improved delivery performance, and faster development, Melton (2005); Karam et al. (2018).

To remain active in competitive conditions of marketing for different production companies, efficient adoption of lean production has created potential for continuous development, Upadhye et al. (2010). The lean manufacturing concepts and techniques may greatly enhance a manufacturer's performance by focusing on main production wastes such as overproduction, waiting, transportation, overprocessing, inventory, movement, faulty components, human inventiveness, and time in production phases, Elnamrouy and Abushaaban (2013).

Seven wastes in processes and resources were identified by the Toyota Production System which cannot add value to the produced parts de Bucourt et al. (2011). These seven wastes are unnecessary transportation, excess inventory, unnecessary motion of people,

equipment, or machinery, waiting, whether it is people waiting or idle equipment, over-production of a product, over-processing, or investing more time in a product than a customer requires, such as designs that necessitate high-tech machinery for unnecessary features and defects, which necessitate effort and cost to correct, Teichgräber and de Bucourt (2012). Figure 1 depicts the four different types of trigger signals that influence a manufacturer's decision to start using the LP philosophy to manage production processes, Yusup et al. (2013).

Figure 1: Lean production trigger signals, Yusup et al. (2013).

Six important success variables of lean production methodologies are as 1- Make sure there's a lot of managerial support, 2- Encourage full employee engagement, 3- Set up enough time to prepare the organization, 4- Concentrate on instilling enthusiasm to accomplish projects, 5- Develop internal organizational competency, 6- Create a mechanism for evaluating performance, Netland (2016); Alhuraish et al. (2017). Despite the many advantages of lean, there are still certain obstacles that make it feasible to oppose its implementation. Poor psychology, a lack of accountability, financial issues, a lack of knowledge and training, and demand volatility are just a few of the primary negatives that act as roadblocks to lean implementation, Gupta and Jain (2013).

The foundation and implementation of lean production system in the Indian manufacturing industry is studied in order to improve productivity in the component production process, Jasti and Kodali (2019). An inquiry of lean manufacturing practices in the mining

industry is developed in order to enhance efficiency and added value in the mining companies, Lööw (2018). In order to enhance productivity in the advanced process of part manufacture, a systematic literature review of Industry 4.0 tools in lean production is presented by Gallo et al. (2021). The use of simulation in lean production research is investigated in order to improve the impacts of simulation and analysis in terms of improving part production efficiency, Shou et al. (2021). In order to avoid Lean implementation failures in the automobile industry, Lean production in Toyota Production System and Kaizen philosophy are reviewed by Chiarini et al. (2018). To improve management strategies in efficiency enhancement of part manufacturing, modelling management behaviours in lean production systems is studied by Camuffo and Gerli (2018).

The review of the six sigma versus lean manufacturing is presented by Ikumapayi et al. (2020) in order to increase the benefits of the six sigma methods in the efficiency enhancement of lean production systems. Lean manufacturing and human resources is reviewed by Koemtzi et al. (2022) in order to analyze the effects of human cultures to the success rates of the lean manufacturing implementation. A review in lean manufacturing implementation and methodologies is presented by Kumar et al. (2022) in order to improve the success rate in efficiency enhancement by the advanced lean production systems. To increase the effects of lean production methods in productivity enhancement of part production, applications of the Internet of Things (IoT) and decision support systems are analyzed by Abd Rahman et al. (2021). Influence of lean manufacturing on firms' financial performance is reviewed by Dieste et al. (2021) in order to analyze and increase the financial outcomes by implementation of the lean production systems.

Soori et al. provide virtual machining methodologies to assess and improve CNC machining in virtual worlds, Soori et al. (2017); Soori et al. (2014); Soori et al. (2013); Soori et al. (2016). A review in advanced virtual machining systems is presented by Soori and Arezoo (2020) in order to increase the impacts of virtual simulation and analysis to efficiency enhancement of part production. Soori et al. (2020) provides a review of current developments in friction stir welding techniques in order to examine and improve efficiency in the process of component manufacturing employing welding procedures. Soori and Asmael (2021c) have explored implementations of virtual machining systems to reduce residual stress and deflection error throughout turbine blade five-axis milling processes. Soori and Asmael (2021a) created implementations of virtualized machining system in evaluating and decreasing the cutting temperature throughout milling operations of hard to cut components. To analyze and minimize

the residual stress during metal cutting operations, a review in machining induced residual stress is presented by Soori and Arezoo (2022).

Soori et al. (2021) proposed an improved virtual machining method to improve surface properties throughout five-axis milling operations of turbine blades. Soori and Asmael (2021b) devised virtual milling techniques to reduce deflection error during five-axis milling processes of impeller blades. Soori and Asmael (2022) provided a summary of existing developments from published articles in order to examine and improve the parameter optimization technique of machining processes. Dastres et al. (2022) presented a study of Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) based wireless manufacturing systems to improve energy utilization efficiency, data quality and availability across the supply chain and precision and dependability during the component production process.

To develop the decision support systems in the data warehouse management, advances in web-based decision support systems is studied by Dastres and Soori (2021a). To develop the applications of the artificial neural networks in different areas such as risk analysis systems, drone control, welding quality analysis and computer quality analysis, a review in recent development and applications of the systems is presented by Dastres and Soori (2021b). Applications of the information communication technology in the environmental protection is presented by Dastres and Soori (2021c) in order to decrease the effects of technology development to the natural disaster.

In this paper, a review in applications of the lean production systems in efficiency enhancement of part manufacturing is presented. Lean manufacturing tools and elements, lean production systems for industry 4.0, Sustainable manufacturing by lean production systems, lean production international supply chain, lean tools and techniques in automotive industries and assembly line design in lean manufacturing are considered in order to review the recent development in the advanced lean production systems from the published papers. Applications of the different tools and methodologies in implementations of the advanced lean production systems is reviewed in the paper to analyse and enhance the success rates of the lean production methods in productivity enhancement of part production. The combinations of the advanced production managements and lean production systems are reviewed in order to develop the process of production planning systems. By reviewing and evaluating previous published papers, the goal of this article is to examine the impacts of lean production on the improvement of part production productivity. It hopes that new ideas can be introduced by reviewing and analyzing recent achievements from published papers to increase the productivity in the advanced lean manufacturing systems.

2. LEAN MANUFACTURING TOOLS AND ELEMENTS

Organizations of the advanced lean production system is under influence of different lean manufacturing technologies, production processes and strategies. To eliminate anything that does not add value to a product as waste of resources, advanced lean manufacturing techniques and tools are developed. Lean manufacturing tools are designed to help eliminate waste, streamline processes, increase quality control, and make the most of manufacturing resources, Leksic et al. (2020); Karam et al. (2018). Figure 2 depicts the elements of lean manufacturing, Singh et al. (2018).

Figure 2: Elements and tools of lean manufacturing, Singh et al. (2018).

2.1 Just in Time (JIT)

Just-in-time (JIT) inventory management is a way of receiving items from suppliers just when they are required. This method's major goal is to lower inventory holding costs and boost inventory turnover Lou et al. (2015). The JIT method aims to reduce waste and increase production by simplifying manufacturing operations and reducing inventory levels. JIT entails producing only what is necessary, when it is required, and in the amount required at that moment, Stojkanović et al. (2021). JIT inventory management boosts productivity by lowering production time and resources. As a result, manufacturing is faster and production runs are shorter due to implementation of lean manufacturing, Phan et al. (2019). Because, there are fewer raw materials on hand, the process planning can make product adjustments more rapidly, França et al. (2018). Preventing overproduction, reducing waiting times and transportation costs, saving resources by streamlining your production systems, reducing the capital you have

tied up in stock, eliminating the need for inventory operations, and reducing product defects are just a few of the benefits of just-in-time delivery, Suri and Burke (2020). The downsides of Just-in-Time (JIT) Manufacturing include the possibility of running out of stock and reliance on suppliers. Relying on suppliers' timelessness for each order puts you at risk of delaying your customers' reception of goods, Milewski (2022).

2.2 Heijunka

The Japanese term for "levelling" is heijunka, Lippolt and Furmans (2008). Heijunka is the concept of levelling a production system by eliminating volume fluctuations produced regarding the batch processing and customer order fluctuations in order to achieve a mixed model production system with a consistent flow of components. Production smoothing or levelling aims to maintain a continuous flow of production by delivering work to the plant at the appropriate rate and eliminating disruptions, Romero et al. (2018). In lean production theory, the notion of heijunk which is controlling the unpredictability of the work arrival sequence to allow for improved capacity utilization is crucial, Hüttmeir et al. (2009); Bautista-Valhondo (2021). Heijunka is designed to reduce batching while balancing the kind and quantity of output García Rivera (2018). The Ford company is known for producing automobiles in batches while the Toyota company employed Heijunka to reduce batching and make their production process more efficient, Rüttimann and Stöckli (2016). Heijunka's mission is to minimize inventory, capital expenditures, personnel and manufacturing time. Heijunka is the best adaptation methodology when advanced lean production methods previously implemented and the waste parameters of resources are clearly recognized, Tecnovalvo et al. (2021).

2.3.Kanban

The Japanese name for "Signal Card" is Kanban. When a part was running low in the past, factory employees would fill up a signal card, Rao et al. (2021). Kanban is a signal that is used to streamline operations and deliver goods just-in-time. Physical signals, such as a tag or an empty container, can be delivered physically or electronically through a system. Kanban's primary purpose is to decrease waste in the process of part production. The goal of Kanban is to enhance flow by communicating tasks, progress, and restrictions in a clear, visible manner, Ahmad et al. (2018); Lei et al. (2017). The signal card would be forwarded to a team or employee whose duty it was to place an order for more of that particular part. The kanban procedure is now largely computerized in order to increase the benefits of the methods in the productivity enhancement of part production, Papalexi et al. (2016). The goal behind Kanban

is to only acquire new parts when they are actually required. However, if components are purchased automatically without understanding if they are required, a company's profitability can be harmed, Hofmann and Rüsç (2017).

2.4.5S

5S is an approach for creating a clean, uncluttered, safe, and well-organized workplace in order to decrease waste and increase productivity. It's intended to aid in the creation of a positive work environment, both physically and mentally, Abu Bakar et al. (2019). It is a collection of procedures for arranging workplaces in order to produce efficient, productive, and safe environments for workers, as well as to avoid wasting time and effort, Alemán Rentas (2019). Sort, Set in Order, Shine, Standardize, and Sustain are the five steps of the 5S approach, Mahlaha et al. (2020). These processes entail looking over everything in a place, evaluating what is and isn't required, organizing, cleaning, and establishing systems for executing these duties on a regular basis, Costa et al. (2018). The five steps of 5S are shown in the figure 3.

Figure 3: The five steps of 5S.

2.5.Jidoka

Jidoka refers to the discovery of flaws in the manufacturing process, whereas SMED refers to the reduction of preparation time. When an abnormal scenario for the machine or operators develops, Jidoka has the ability to automatically recognize the system and stop production. Producing flawless goods, enhancing quality, preventing the failure of machinery, tools and equipment of production and keeping processes safe are all ways to achieve high-quality products and increased productivity, Tekin et al. (2018); Rewers et al. (2016). It is a process for recognizing abnormalities, suspending work until they can be remedied, fixing the problem, and then analyzing the root cause, Deuse et al. (2020). "Intelligent automation" or "humanized automation" is what Jidoka or Autonomation signifies, Deuse et al. (2020). In

practice, this implies that an automated process is sufficiently "conscious" of itself to recognize process or product faults, stop itself, and notify the operator, Ohno and Bodek (2019).

2.6.KAIZEN

The Japanese word kaizen means "continuous improvement." The word refers to operations to enhance every aspect of an organization. It is most commonly associated with manufacturing, although it may be used to practically any industry, Rüttimann and Stöckli (2016). Kaizen is a Japanese concept that aims to enhance established processes in order to reduce waste, increase productivity, and address business problems, DIMITRESCU et al. (2018). The five major phases of the Kaizen approach are as, 1- Determine the issue area that will be addressed, 2- Analyze present procedure using videotape, 3- Put improvement strategies to the test and assess them, 4- Make improvements to the situation, 5- Analyze the findings and give them to higher management for comment, Chiarini, Baccarani and Mascherpa (2018). Kaizen is based on the 5S framework, which prioritizes waste removal and standardization, Randhawa and Ahuja (2017). The 5S method establishes a solid platform for future Kaizen operations. 5S is an organizational approach in which everyone in the business helps to clear clutter and organize workspaces, Katare and Yadav (2019).

3. LEAN PRODUCTION SYSTEMS FOR INDUSTRY 4.0

The lean manufacturing production technique is a mindset that works in tandem with Industry 4.0 developments to assist efficiency initiatives across the manufacturing process ,Tortorella and Fettermann (2018); Sharma et al. (2020). Both Lean and Industry 4.0 are industrial concepts that serve as a foundation for designing production processes, Leyh et al. (2017). Unlike Industry 4.0, which focuses on new technology to solve today's challenges, Lean is a technology enemy whose philosophy revolves upon people, processes, and a culture of continuous improvement, Tortorella et al. (2019); Florescu and Barabas (2022). At first look, it may appear that the Lean principles of people orientation and simplicity are incompatible with Industry 4.0's cutting-edge digital and automated technology, Tortorella and Fettermann (2018); Satoglu et al. (2018). The objective of the lean–green approach works in the present scenario of Industry 4.0 is shown in the figure 4, Tripathi et al. (2021).

Figure 4: Objectives of smart lean–green approach, Tripathi et al. (2021).

In order to improve efficiency in the part manufacturing process, the determinants of lean production and the performance consequences of implementing Industry 4.0 in Thailand are studied by Hotrawaisaya et al. (2019). The impact of Industry 4.0 and lean manufacturing on European enterprises is being investigated in order to improve the efficiency of part manufacturing processes, Rossini et al. (2019). The 4.0 assessment model for manufacturing SMEs is studied in order to establish techniques for increasing productivity via the use of lean manufacturing and industry 4.0, Kolla et al. (2019). The contributions of lean thinking to Industry 4.0 are examined in order to further develop lean manufacturing applications for improving part production efficiency, Bittencourt et al. (2019).

4. SUSTAINABLE MANUFACTURING BY LEAN PRODUCTION SYSTEMS

Designing a sustainable manufacturing system requires consideration of both economic and environmental restrictions. Business concerns about sustainable business strategies and environmental accounting are developing. However, there are a variety of methods for calculating an organization's or supply chain's entire environmental footprint, and there is currently no agreed-upon uniform standard, Heilala et al. (2008). Manufacturing has a significant impact on global development and progress, and this trend is projected to continue as a result of rising demand for consumer products from a growing global population with improving living standards, Haapala et al. (2013). Manufacturing is critical to the global economy's success with the sustainable methodologies. Manufacturing not only provides items to customers and industries all over the world, but it also contributes significantly to

employment, community presence, and economic power, Duflou et al. (2012). Figure 5 depicts a hypothetical paradigm combining lean manufacturing and sustainability, Resta et al. (2016).

Figure 5: The conceptual model of lean manufacturing and sustainability, Resta et al. (2016).

In order to boost added values in the part production process, perspectives of lean and sustainable manufacturing are explored by Vinodh and Asokan (2018). The link between lean-green manufacturing practices and sustainability is examined in order to provide new ideas for developing lean manufacturing methodologies, Abualfaraa et al. (2020).

5. KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT IN LEAN PRODUCTION SYSTEMS

In the lean production systems, knowledge management (KM) has become one of the most important words. Knowledge management include the processes of developing, safeguarding, capturing, coordinating, merging, retrieving, and disseminating information in order to provide advanced lean production, Dombrowski et al. (2012). In order to establish lean sustainability in the production process, lean tools, knowledge management, and lean sustainability are studied by Zhang et al. (2020). In order to support collaborative decision making in lean supply chain management, a decision-focused knowledge management paradigm is developed by Liu et al. (2013). To increase product value and minimize product life cycle cost by adopting better technology and processes, the combination of DFSS, lean product development, and lean knowledge management is proposed by Yang and Cai (2009). In order to boost efficiency in the component manufacturing process, a learning factory strategy for digital shop floor management is provided, which uses digitalization as a catalyst for lean

production, Meissner et al. (2018). In the Fourth Industrial Revolution, knowledge management is studied in order to enhance added value in the process of part manufacture via lean manufacturing, Manesh et al. (2020). In order to provide lean services using knowledge management, Toyota Kata as a KM solution to the inhibitors of implementing lean service in service companies is proposed by Ferenhof et al. (2018).

6. LEAN PRODUCTION IN INTERNATIONAL SUPPLY CHAIN

Lean manufacturing facilitates the integration of multiple tools in the production system and supply chain, with the goal of reducing costs, improving quality, and reducing lead time, inventory, and equipment downtime, Marodin et al. (2016). Shorter, simpler distribution networks result from a Lean supply chain's focus on lowering lead times Ponte et al. (2018). Lean is also used in warehouses and freight networks to reduce non-value-added waste including long journey times, waiting periods, and wasteful double handling of goods, Villarreal et al. (2016). In order to boost productivity in the automobile production process, lean production and operational performance in the Brazilian automotive supply chain are studied, Marodin et al. (2019). In order to offer supply chain integration and improved business performance, the business results influence on lean manufacturing management (lean production implementation) and supply chain integration settings is studied, Novais et al. (2020). Lean integration in the healthcare supply chain is examined in order to improve hospital service quality to the patients, Borges et al. (2019). To improve operational performance in the component manufacturing process, researchers linked supply logistics integration, supply performance, lean processes, and competitive performance, Prajogo et al. (2016).

7. LEAN TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES IN AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRIES

In order to increase the efficiency in automotive industries, applications of the lean production systems are developed in different research works, Nordin et al. (2010); Azevedo et al. (2019); Sahoo (2020). The automotive industry's quality and flexibility performance trade-offs are studied to determine the link between flexibility and quality and to investigate the quality and flexibility variations between lean and agile production, Qamar et al. (2020). TPM is used in conjunction with 5S to increase the availability of an automobile production line Ribeiro et al. (2019). To increase productivity in automotive industries, lean manufacturing and ergonomic working conditions in the automotive industry is studied, dos Santos et al. (2015). Figure 6 depicts a roadmap for Lean deployment in the Indian automobile component manufacturing industry, Jadhav et al. (2015).

Figure 6: Roadmap for Lean deployment in the Indian automobile component manufacturing industry Jadhav, Mantha and Rane (2015).

In order to provide optimized lean production systems in terms of productivity enhancement of part manufacturing, visualizing knowledge for decision-making in Lean Production Development settings in the automotive sectors is studied, Canonico et al. (2021). In order to provide sophisticated lean production systems in the automobile industry, flexibility trade-offs within the automotive supply chain are studied by Qamar et al. (2018).

8. ASSEMBLY LINE DESIGN IN LEAN MANUFACTURING

Through value stream mapping, lean manufacturing is increasingly being used to redesign and enhance assembly line designs, Qattawi and Chalil Madathil (2019). Lean manufacturing tools are used to change an assembly line, so that nonvalue-added operations can be eliminated, resulting in continual improvement Álvarez et al. (2009). Re-engineering Manufacturing Lines using Lean Techniques is used to improve the efficiency of the electronic device assembly process, Nguyen and Do (2016). Manual assembly lines for complicated electrical gadgets are being designed using Lean technologies to improve line efficiency and output rate, Correia et al. (2018). To increase and sustain performance over time, complexity reduction and kaizen events are used to balance manual assembly lines, Cannas et al. (2018). In order to minimize superfluous inventory, reduce total cycle time, and total setup time at multiple assembly stations, a lean manufacturing implementation at an excavator

manufacturing business by employing value stream mapping is demonstrated, Masuti and Dabade (2019). To improve the production rate of assembly lines in low added-value products, lean tools are applied, Rosa et al. (2018). To develop the assembly line design, an Industry 4.0 approach using lean production method is implemented, Rossit et al. (2019). In order to boost productivity in the assembly line of the automotive industry, a lean evaluation tool for workstation design of assembly lines is proposed, Gonçalves and Salonitis (2017).

9. CONCLUSION

Lean manufacturing is a production approach that focuses on minimizing cycle times inside the production system as well as reaction times from suppliers and customers. Unnecessary transportation, excess inventory, unnecessary movement of people, equipment or machinery, over-production of a product, waiting either people or idle equipment, over processing or adding unnecessary features to a product and defects that require costly correction are wastes that don't provide value to the customer which should be minimized by the lean manufacturing systems. Smoother production processes, shorter cycle times, fewer inventory, and lower production costs are all advantages of lean manufacturing. Only dealing with the materials, equipment, and labor necessary to satisfy present demand is the main aim of lean business entail. Automation has broadened lean manufacturing concepts with technologies aimed at decreasing human operator error while yet adhering to lean production principles.

Cloud software, autonomous robots, machine learning, and the Internet of things can be used to improve the productivity of advanced lean manufacturing systems. The lean production systems can be applied to the green production regarding the amount of energy consumption of the part production process. As a result, the new sources of green energy can be used in terms of cleaner production process. Hybrid cloud manufacturing system as well as web-based approach in the advanced lean production systems can be used in order to provide new lean production methodologies. Advanced resource scheduling regarding the cleaner production can be provided in order to enhanced business performance by adapting to the customers' demands and satisfactions. The applications of the lean production systems in the ship as well as aircraft industries can be applied in order to increase added values in the product planning and manufacturing processes. The small-scale industries can be modified regarding the lean manufacturing in order to increase productivity in the small businesses. Smart manufacturing systems for Industry 4.0 regarding the lean production can be developed in order to provide advanced smart manufacturing systems.

Predictive maintenance of industrial equipment can be modified by applying the lean production concepts in order to decrease the equipment failure rate and production costs of part manufacturing. Lean manufacturing performance can be increased by using fuzzy logic algorithms in order to increase the effects of the lean production systems in the advanced manufacturing. Virtual manufacturing systems can be applied to the lean production methodologies in order to enhance the impacts of virtual simulation to the efficiency enhancement of part production. To increase flexibility and adaptivity of the advanced lean production systems to the new industry 4.0, applications of the machine learning can be developed. Dynamic scheduling of flexible manufacturing systems can be modified regarding the concepts of lean manufacturing systems in terms of productivity enhancement of part production. Real time scheduling flexible manufacturing systems can be optimized by using the lean production methods in order to enhance the impacts of lean applications in efficiency enhancement of part manufacturing. As a result, the modified versions of the lean manufacturing strategies can be presented regarding the suggested future research works in order to increase the productivity in process of part production.

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